

Kinetics of Enolisation of Cyclic Ketones.

Part I. Enolisation of Cyclopentanone

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Investigation of the enolisation of cyclopentanone in acid solutions (0.01 to 0.3 molar) and in buffers (pH 3.2 to 6.0) has been made at 25°. Effects of ionic strengths, pH, solvent, solvent isotope, temperature etc. on the rate of enolisation have been studied in detail to determine bimolecular enolisation via both neutral and conjugate acid species.

ENOLISATION of ketones has been of great academic interest in the history of Chemistry since it is connected with the wellknown phenomenon of tautomerism. The rate of conversion of a keto into enol form has been measured by reactions such as halogenation¹, racemization² and deuteration³. It has been shown that all the above reactions have a common rate-determining step. In acid media the direct conversion of a keto into enol form and indirect conversion of keto into enol form via the rate determining formation of the mesomeric anion from the former have been observed⁴. Bimolecular attack of a base on the hydrogen atom has been shown to be promoted by hyperconjugative effect in acid media⁵ and by inductive effects in basic solutions⁶. The above study has been almost mainly concentrated to open chain ketones, particularly acetone and to acetophenone and almost no kinetic work is available on cyclic ketones. It is interesting therefore to investigate the kinetics of enolisation of the cyclic ketones. The present paper deals with the kinetics and mechanism of enolisation of cyclopentanone.

Materials and Methods

Cyclopentanone was of Fluka A.R. quality, B.P. 129°. Acids and all other chemicals were of analytical grade.

The rates of enolisation of cyclopentanone (0.1M unless otherwise specified) were measured by rates of iodination⁷ by traditional method. The temperature of the thermostat was 25° ± 0.05°. The deuterium oxide (Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay) was of isotopic purity more than 99.4%. Buffer solutions for kinetic experiments were used as in the case of dimethyl phosphate⁸. Constant ionic strengths were maintained by using HCl and NaCl.

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Results and Discussion

Enolisation of conjugate acid species

Enolisation of cyclopentanone at 25° in the acid region (0.01 to 0.2M HCl, 0.02 to 0.2M HClO₄, 0.02 to 0.2M H₂SO₄) rises linearly with the rise in acidity. First order rate coefficients are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE I. RATE COEFFICIENTS OF ENOLISATION OF CYCLOPENTANONE IN HCl, HClO₄ AND H₂SO₄
TEMPERATURE = 25°

[Cyclopentanone] = 0.1M

Acid M	2 + log (Acid M)	k × 10 ³ . min ⁻¹ .		
		HCl	HClO ₄	H ₂ SO ₄
0.02	0.3010	2.593	2.364	4.435
0.05	0.6990	7.151	5.918	9.109
0.08	0.9031	10.207	10.27	17.33
0.10	1.00	12.015	12.21	22.99
0.12	1.0792	14.67	14.73	25.98
0.15	1.1761	16.002	15.91	30.90
0.20	1.3010	17.310	17.63	37.41

Effect of ionic strength

Sometimes the elevation in rates in acid medium may be caused due to positive ionic strength effect⁹, hence kinetic runs have been made at constant ionic strength and the first order rate coefficients have been summarised in Table 2. A plot between rate constants and acidity gives linear curves which prove that enolisation occurs via conjugate acid species. Since the slopes decrease with the increase in ionic strength, the acid catalysed enolisation is subject to negative effect of ionic strength. The intercepts indicate enolisation via neutral species the rate of which increases with the

increase in ionic strength. Both these rates may be represented as :

$$k_{H^+} = k_{H_3O^+} \times \exp.b_{H^+}\mu \quad \dots (1)$$

and

$$k_N = k_{N_0} \times \exp. b_{N^0}\mu \quad \dots (2)$$

TABLE 2. EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTHS ON REACTION RATE IN HCl ON ENOLISATION OF CYCLOPENTANONE
TEMPERATURE = 25°

[Cyclopentanone] = 0.1M			
HCl (M)	NaCl (M)	Ionic Strength (μ)	k $\times 10^3$ (min. ⁻¹)
0.02	0.08	0.1	2.341
0.05	0.05	0.1	6.062
0.08	0.02	0.1	8.34
0.10	0.00	0.1	12.015
0.05	0.15	0.2	7.310
0.10	0.10	0.2	9.591
0.15	0.05	0.2	13.625
0.20	0.00	0.2	15.263
0.08	0.07	0.25	9.804
0.12	0.13	0.25	12.201
0.18	0.07	0.25	17.15
0.25	0.00	0.25	21.78

where k_{H^+} , k_N are specific acid catalysed and specific neutral rates at a given ionic strength (μ) respectively. b_{H^+} and b_N are constants; $k_{H_3O^+}$, k_{N_0} , b_{H^+} and b_N can be calculated by plotting log rates against ionic strength (μ). Results are summarised in table 3. The estimated rates from the above equations are in close agreement with the experimental rates, and therefore the overall enolisation may be represented as :

$$k_e = k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} + k_N$$

TABLE 3. ACID AND NEUTRAL RATES FOR THE ENOLISATION OF CYCLOPENTANONE

Temperature = 25°

[Cyclopentanone] = 0.1M

HCl (M)	10 ³ × neutral rates	10 ³ × Acid rates	10 ³ × (sum of neutral and acid rates)	10 ³ × (observed rates from Table 1)
0.01	0.2259	1.462	1.687	1.625
0.02	0.2553	2.5053	2.761	2.593
0.05	0.3698	6.4150	6.785	7.151
0.08	0.5352	9.3040	9.839	10.207
0.10	0.685	10.89	11.575	12.015
0.12	0.8766	14.604	15.471	14.670
0.20	2.352	15.676	18.028	17.310

Effect of Temperature

The Arrhenius parameters for the iodination of cyclopentanone in 0.02, 0.05 and 0.1M HCl were determined over temperature of 30°. Results are

summarised in Table 4. It is clear from the results that the parameters belong to only acid catalysed reaction because the contribution of the neutral rates to the overall reaction in the acid range is negligibly small (Table 3).

TABLE 4. ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR THE ENOLISATION OF CYCLOPENTANONE VIA CONJUGATE ACID SPECIES

HCl (M)	E K.Cal. mole. ⁻¹	A min. ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.
0.02	20.3	6.9×10^{12}	-12.3
0.05	20.3	2.1×10^{12}	-10.3
0.10	20.0	5.1×10^{12}	-10.1

Solvent Isotope Effect

Specific acid catalysed enolisation of cyclopentanone would involve a pre-equilibrium fast proton transfer for the conversion of a neutral into conjugate acid species. A change over from water to deuterium oxide as a solvent should then make the reaction faster. The $k_{D_2^0}/k_{H_2^0} > 1$ is generally associated with acid catalysis¹⁰⁻¹². The solvent isotope effect for the enolisation of cyclopentanone in 0.04M hydrochloric acid at 25° apparently indicates specific acid catalysis because of elevation of rate in D₂O. ($k_{D_2^0}/k_{H_2^0} = 1.29$). This is also supported by the smooth pH—log rate profile obtained for the enolisation in buffers.

Effect of solvent

A change over to a solvent of more ionising power could greatly increase the reaction rates, if the charges are created in the transition state, whereas rate will be reduced but to a slight extent if the transition state is such which involves dispersion of the charge of unchanged magnitude. Thus the results of Table 5 indicate the formation of transition state in which charges are not created. Bimolecular enolisation of the conjugate acid species of the cyclopentanone should involve the dispersion of positive charge with its magnitude unchanged.

TABLE 5. RATE COEFFICIENTS OF ENOLISATION OF CYCLOPENTANONE IN AQUEOUS DIOXAN MIXTURES

Temperature = 25°
(Cyclopentanone) = 0.1M

HCl (M)	% of Dioxan V/v	k $\times 10^3$ (min. ⁻¹)
	20	7.151
0.05	30	6.826
0.05	40	6.301
0.05	50	6.640
0.05	60	6.432
0.05	70	6.112
0.05	80	6.210

Zucker-Hammett hypothesis suggests the probable mechanism to be bimolecular, if the slope of the curve between log-rate and log C_{H^+} is approximately unity. Zucker-Hammett plots for the enolisation

of cyclopentanone in hydrochloric, perchloric and sulphuric acids give approximately unit slopes

On the basis of the above experimental evidences the mechanism of the enolisation of cyclopentanone via its conjugate acid species may be formulated as :

- (a) Formation of the conjugate acid of the cyclopentanone as a fast pre-equilibrium proton transfer :

- (b) Bimolecular attack of water on the conjugate acid species :

Enolisation of Neutral species

Iodination of cyclopentanone which is presumed to be the same as its enolisation at 25° in the range pH 3.2 to 6.0 can be represented as :

$$k_{\text{obsd.}} = k_{N_0} \times \text{fraction of the neutral species.}$$

Plot of $\log k$ vs pH for enolisation of cyclopentanone shows that the rate of enolisation is almost constant in the above region. The reactive species in this region being the bulk neutral species the observed rate ($k_{N_0} = 0.198 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min.}^{-1}$) is the specific neutral rate. The presumption is supported by the specific neutral rate $k_{N_2O} (0.199 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min.}^{-1})$ estimated from ionic strength data. The contribution by the neutral rate to the overall reaction in the acid media may be represented by equation (2).

Temperature effect

Kinetic study of the enolisation of cyclopentanone in pH 3.2 to 6.0 buffer at a series of temperatures shows the uniformity of the reaction (Arrhenius plots not given). Arrhenius parameters ($E = 14.3 \text{ Kcal.mole}^{-1}$, $A = 1.4 \times 10^7 \text{ min.}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -33.5 \text{ e.u.}$) determined from the Arrhenius plot at 3.2 pH (not given) are quite distinct from the acid catalysed enolisation indicating the presence of a new reaction path. They are in accord with bimolecular enolisation because the part of water in rate determining step will lead to a more rigid transition state which may give rise to high negative value of entropy of activation and probably a small activation energy.¹³

Solvent Isotope Effect

In absence of acid catalysed enolisation deuterium oxide (a weak base), if used in place of water (a more

powerful base) as a solvent, is expected to cause lowering in rate of bimolecular enolisation. The lowering in rate in D₂O ($k_{D_2O}/k_{H_2O} = 0.6301$) at 25° for the enolisation of cyclopentanone at pH 3.2 indicates the reaction to be bimolecular.

Mechanism of enolisation of cyclopentanone via its neutral species may be formulated as :

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References

1. P. D. Bartlett and C. H. Stauffer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **75**, 2580.
2. S. D. Shu, C. K. Ingold and C. L. Wilson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 78.
3. K. F. Bonhoeffer and O. Reitz, *Physik Chem.*, A, 1937, 179.
4. H. L. Heys, "Electronic Theory of Organic Compounds", George G. Harrap and Co. Ltd., London, 1960, 196.
5. D. P. Evans and J. R. Young, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1314.
6. E. S. Gould, "Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Holt Rinehart and Winston, New York, 1964, p. 384.
7. K. H. Meyer, *Ann.*, 1911, **38**, 212.
K. H. Meyer and Kappelmeier, *Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 2718.
8. C. A. Bunton, M. M. Mhala, K. G. Oldham and C. A. Vernon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3293.
9. C. K. Ingold, "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry". Bell and Sons, London, 1953, p. 345.
10. P. W. D. Barnard, C. A. Bunton, D. Kellerman, M. M. Mhala, B. Silver, C. S. Vernon and V. A. Welch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, B, 1960, 227.
11. C. A. Bunton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 1221.
12. R. P. Bell, "Acid-base Catalysis", Oxford University Press, London, 1941.
13. C. A. Bunton and V. J. Shiner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 42, 3207, 3214.